

Investigation on improvised explosive devices and the physicochemical nature of the fuel binders

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Abstract : Exhibits of a series of bomb blasts (IED or Improvised Explosive Devices) in Southern parts of West Bengal, sent to the CFSL (Central Forensic Science Laboratory) showed that the explosives contained ammonium nitrate, sodium/potassium nitrate, traces of chlorides, sulfate etc. and paint grade aluminum powder with fuels sparingly soluble in acetone but soluble in ether. Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometric analysis of fuel oils (1-6) and fuels in the explosives indicated the absence of fuel oils. GC-MS analysis of ethereal solutions of wax collected from candle sticks available in the market showed the fuels used in the explosives were easily available ordinary wax though a number of explosives contained synthetic wax as apparent from GC-MS.

The fuel contents in the explosives were 3.3–6.2% for ordinary waxes but 8.9–11.2% for synthetic waxes probably related to high melting and low melting points of the natural waxes and synthetic waxes.

The results showed that IED's were not truly ANFO as reported earlier. The ethereal solutions of the waxes showed fluorescence but the excitation maxima and the fluorescence maxima were similar indicating the similarities of the hydrocarbons present with changes in molecular weights in the hydrocarbon fractions of the fuel.

Keywords : Aluminium powder, ammonium nitrate, ANFO, fluorescence, fuel oils, gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer, hydrocarbons, ion chromatograph, waxes.

Introduction

Explosives were utilized not only for military purpose but extensively used for blasting operation, construction of roads and tunnels, mining and quarries¹. Apart from military uses, dynamites were used extensively as potential blasting devices for peaceful commercial purposes mentioned before. The use of dynamites in mines caused gas and dust explosions with heavy casualties². Moreover, efforts were also made for suitable substitutes of dynamite by less costly products. Ever since the explosion of ammonium nitrate (AN) coated with wax loaded ship in Texas with vast casualties, AN came into prominence as explosive³. But water resistance is the criteria of explosive in mines and quarries which are usually wet and holes drilled for charging the explosives got filled with water i.e. suitability of AN as a blasting agent in mines etc. was in doubt. The problem was overcome using AN with fuel oil technically known as ANFO. ANFO

became a kind of deadly bomb that shocked Oklahoma city. ANFO was widely used as commercial blasting agents. However since the compound are readily available, AN and fuel oil or ANFO has been extensively used by the terrorist to prepare IED.

Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata regularly receives a large number of Improvised Explosive Devices or FED's seized by different law enforcing authorities for forensic investigations and reporting.

The results of the investigative analysis of some of the 'Improvised Explosive Devices' are presented in this communication.

Experimental

IED (exploded and unexploded) samples received from the law enforcing authorities collected from different places of West Bengal and adjacent areas were the experimental samples. Acetone, ether and other organic solvents used

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were of HPLC grade from E. Merck (India). Standard fuel oils (1–6, except 5) from Supelco containing (20000–50000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of fuel) were used for comparative study of fuels used in the explosives assumed to be ANFO. Candle sticks were collected from the market. The samples contained essentially water soluble parts and oil soluble parts.

However, fuels obtained in case of these explosives are partially soluble in acetone but they were soluble in ethereal solutions indicating the absence of fuel oils. The ethereal solutions of the exhibits were subjected to GC/MS studies. GC/MS studies of natural wax and solutions from standard candle sticks readily available in the market in ethereal solutions were also made.

For inorganic materials present in the exhibits, routine tests for metal and non-metal ions present were performed using standard procedures suggested in the literature^{5,6}. Ion chromatographic analysis as recommended by FBI^{7,8} were also done to confirm the presence of ions. However only qualitative studies were made. For the standardization and calibration in IC (Ion chromatograph) NIST traceable standards were used. All the inorganic compounds used for experimental purposes were of AnalaR grade from E. Merck. Ultrapure deionized water of resistivity 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega$ was used for preparation of aqueous solutions. The inorganic parts contained AN (NH_4^+ , NO_3^- ions) mainly determined by ion chromatography and Al mainly with the minor constituents like Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , nitrates with other ingredients like Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} . However ClO_3^- , $\text{As}^{3+/5+}$, S^{2-} were found to be absent.

Instruments :

(A) Ion chromatograph :

A Metrohm (Switzerland) conductivity detector (suppressor module) with Metrosepp A supp 3 column (for anion), Cation 1–2 column and Nucleosil 5 SA column (both for cation) were used for the detection and estimation of inorganic ions (as recommended by FBI⁷⁻⁹).

(B) GC-MS instrument :

The identification and characterization of the explosives and hydrocarbons present as petroleum base materials were made using Perkin-Elmer Claurus 500 model GC-MS by injecting variable volumes of the experimental solutions in acetone (for explosives) and in ether (for petroleum products) through Elite 5 MS column. Oven

temperature was programmed between 70 °C (1 min) and 300 °C (10 min) with 10 °C/min increment. The injector and interface temperatures were 150 °C and 200 °C. The system was run at constant flow mode, the rate of carrier gas (helium) flow being 1 ml/min, MS parameters for the analysis of explosives were : EI mode, source temperature 150°, energy 70 eV, mass range scanned 30–400 amu.

(C) Spectrofluorometer :

Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer was used for fluorescence measurements. The instruments were first standardized and calibrated using fluorescein. The fluorescence spectra and fluorescence maxima of the experimental solutions were measured using different excitation wavelengths to select the excitation wavelength giving maximum fluorescence intensity and the wavelength of fluorescence maximum. Conversely excitation spectra were measured using the wavelength of fluorescence maxima as a cross-check.

Results

Preliminary experiments in aqueous solutions and IC measurements of inorganic ions present in the exhibits (processed explosive residues from the blast debris) showed the dominance of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- ions, together with Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} ions etc. in minute amounts with varying quantities. A typical IC curve is presented in Fig. 1. No attempt was made for the quantification of ions. The exhibits were sparingly soluble in acetone but soluble in ether. Organic explosives like NC, NG, PETN, TNT, RDX etc. were found to be absent from preliminary investigations and GC-MS analysis. GC-MS analysis of ether soluble extracts did not indicate the presence of fuel oils. Typical TIC of GC-MS curves of some fuel oils are presented in Figs. 2 and 3 and the hydrocarbons present in those fuel oils are presented in Tables 1 and 2. But the TIC of GC-MS and hydrocarbons (Fig. 4 and Table 4) present in the ethereal solutions of exhibits were different from those of fuel oils but they resembled the TIC of GC-MS and mass spectra of wax (Fig. 5 and Table 3) used in candle sticks readily available in the market. A typical TIC diagram showing the overlay of wax and explosive sample is presented in Fig. 6. The explosives obtained were relatively recent. There was another class of explosives (relatively older) where TIC and

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of potassium ions in ion chromatograph.

Fig. 2. TIC of no. 2 fuel oil.

Fig. 3. TIC of no. 3 fuel oil.

Fig. 4. TIC of sample I (natural wax base) type.

Table 1. Hydrocarbons present in fuel oil no. 2

Sl. no.	Retention time	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	5.63	Undecane	C ₁₁ H ₂₄	156
2.	6.39	5,6-Dimethyl undecane	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184
3.	6.55	2-Methyl undecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	170
4.	7.04	Dodecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	170
5.	7.22	2,5-Dimethyl undecane	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184
6.	8.03	Hexadecane, 7-methyl	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	240
7.	8.43	Tridecane	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	180
8.	9.44	Phytane	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	170
9.	9.77	Tetradecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	282
10.	10.53	Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
11.	11.04	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
12.	11.81	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
13.	12.26	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
14.	12.78	Heneicosane	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
15.	13.41	Heptadecane	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	240
16.	14.49	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
17.	15.53	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
18.	16.53	Tetracosane	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	338
19.	17.49	Heneicosane	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
20.	18.42	Docosane	C ₂₂ H ₄₆	310

Table 2. Hydrocarbons present in fuel oil no. 3

Sl. no.	Retention time	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	4.28	1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	C ₉ H ₁₂	120
2.	5.08	1,4-Diethylbenzene	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134
3.	5.49	1-Ethyl-3,5-dimethylbenzene	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134
4.	5.96	Benzene-1,2,4,5-tetramethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134
5.	6.01	Benzene-1,2,3,4-tetramethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134
6.	6.45	<i>o</i> -Allyltoluene	C ₁₀ H ₁₂	132
7.	7.08	Napthalene	C ₁₀ H ₈	128
8.	8.44	Tridecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198
9.	8.66	2-Methylnapthalene	C ₁₁ H ₁₀	142
10.	8.87	1-Methylnapthalene	C ₁₁ H ₁₀	142
11.	9.78	Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198
12.	9.95	1-Ethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
13.	10.15	1,5-Dimethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
14.	10.34	1,4-Dimethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
15.	10.39	1,5-Dimethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
16.	10.59	1,3-Dimethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
17.	10.77	2-Ethylnapthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156

Table-2 (contd.)

18.	11.08	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
19.	11.38	Napthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₄	170
20.	11.62	2,3,6-Trimethyl-napthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₄	170
21.	11.72	1,4,5-Trimethyl-napthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₄	170
22.	11.89	1,3,6-Trimethyl-napthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₄	170
23.	12.30	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
24.	13.45	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
25.	13.78	2,2'-Dimethyl-biphenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₄	182
26.	14.52	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
27.	15.56	Tricosane	C ₂₃ H ₄₈	324
28.	15.94	1-Methyl-phenanthrene	C ₁₅ H ₁₂	192
29.	17.28	2,3-Dimethyl-phenanthrene	C ₁₆ H ₁₄	206
30.	17.46	Heneicosane	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
31.	18.35	Docosane	C ₂₂ H ₄₆	310
32.	19.21	Pentacosane	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352

Table 3. Hydrocarbons present in normal wax from market available candle sticks

Sl. no.	Retention time	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	12.21	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
2.	13.36	Heptadecane 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
3.	14.43	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
4.	15.48	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
5.	16.47	Eicosane	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282
6.	17.41	Heneicosane	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
7.	18.34	Hexacosane	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	366
8.	19.21	Nonacosane	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	408
9.	20.08	Pentacosane	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352
10.	20.90	Pentacosane	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352
11.	21.34	Tetracontane	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	562
12.	21.71	Tetratriacontane	C ₃₄ H ₇₀	472
13.	22.11	Hexatriacontane	C ₃₆ H ₇₄	506
14.	22.48	Tetracontane	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	562
15.	22.87	Tritriacontane	C ₃₃ H ₆₈	464
16.	23.24	Tetratetracontane	C ₄₄ H ₉₀	618
17.	23.61	Hexatriacontane	C ₃₆ H ₇₄	506
18.	23.98	Dotriacontane	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	450
19.	24.73	Pentatriacontane	C ₃₅ H ₇₂	492
20.	25.58	Tetrapentacontane	C ₅₄ H ₁₁₀	758
21.	26.55	Tetracontane	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	562
22.	27.68	Pentatriacontane	C ₃₅ H ₇₂	422
23.	29.01	Tetratriacontane	C ₃₄ H ₇₀	472
24.	30.58	Triacontane	C ₃₀ H ₆₂	422

Fig. 5. TIC of market available candle sticks.

Fig. 6. TIC overlay of candle and explosive sample I type.

Table 4. Hydrocarbons present in sample type I (natural wax base)

Sl. no	Retention time	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	12.15	Pentadecane	$C_{15}H_{32}$	212
2.	13.30	Heptadecane	$C_{17}H_{34}$	238
3.	15.43	Nonadecane	$C_{19}H_{40}$	268
4.	16.43	Eicosane	$C_{20}H_{42}$	282
5.	17.39	Heneicosane	$C_{21}H_{44}$	296
6.	18.33	Nonacosane	$C_{29}H_{60}$	408
7.	19.23	Tricosane	$C_{23}H_{48}$	324
8.	20.10	Pentacosane	$C_{25}H_{52}$	352
9.	20.94	Pentacosane	$C_{25}H_{52}$	352
10.	21.75	Tetratriacontane	$C_{44}H_{90}$	618
11.	22.54	Tetratetracontane	$C_{34}H_{70}$	472
12.	23.33	Hexatriacontane	$C_{36}H_{74}$	506
13.	24.11	Hentriacontane	$C_{31}H_{64}$	436
14.	24.90	Pentatriacontane	$C_{35}H_{72}$	422
15.	25.80	Tritetracontane	$C_{43}H_{88}$	604
16.	28.00	Tetrapentacontane	$C_{54}H_{110}$	758

mass spectra of the ethereal solutions of the samples were different as apparent from the Figure and Table (Fig. 7 and Table 5).

The dilute solutions of waxes in ether showed fluorescence. The measured excitation and fluorescence spectra are given in Fig. 8. The wavelengths of the excitation and fluorescence maxima are presented in Table 6.

Discussion

More than 80% explosions worldwide carried out by the terrorists were due to improvised explosive device (IED) made of common and unrestricted inorganic ingredients^{7-9,11,12} (oxidizers and fuels) like Na/KClO₃, K/NaNO₃, As₂S₃, S, C, Al etc. But in recent years there is a spurt in the use of NH₄NO₃ based improvised explosive device. AN and fuel oils (particularly no. 2 fuel oil) were extensively used as blasting agents as well as in IED's. The post blast residues of the explosives as well as unexploded IED explosives, considered to be ANFO, had been analyzed by the explosive laboratory of the Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata.

In a previous paper¹³, reports had been made on the investigative analysis of AN based explosives. The results showed the explosives were mainly ANFO i.e. AN

Fig. 7. TIC of explosive sample II (synthetic wax base) type.

Fig. 8. Fluorescence spectra of a typical sample.

Table 5. Hydrocarbons present in sample type II (synthetic wax base)

Sl. no.	Retention time	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	10.96	Dodecanonitrile	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ N	181
2.	12.19	Tetradecanitrile	C ₁₄ H ₂₇ N	209
3.	12.73	Phenol, 2-methyl-4,6-dinitro	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅ N ₂	198
4.	13.36	Tridecanenitrile	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ N	195
5.	14.13	1-Nitrododecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	215
6.	14.33	Tetradecanoic acid	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228
7.	14.46	Hexadecanitrile	C ₁₆ H ₃₁ N	237
8.	15.53	Heptadecanitrile	C ₁₇ H ₃₃ N	251
9.	16.27	Tricosene	C ₂₃ H ₄₆	322
10.	16.41	Hexadecanoic acid	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256
11.	16.54	Nonadecanitrile	C ₁₉ H ₃₇ N	279
12.	19.34	Octadecanitrile	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ N	265
13.	19.89	Cyclohexane-1,2-dimethyl-3-pentyl-4-propyl	C ₁₆ H ₃₂	224
14.	19.99	Cyclodocosane, ethyl	C ₂₄ H ₄₈	336

Table-5 (contd.)

15.	21.63	Pentadecane, 8-hexyl	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
16.	22.63	Eicosanenitrile	C ₂₀ H ₃₉ N	293
17.	23.84	Triacotane	C ₃₀ H ₆₂	422
18.	24.58	Nonacosane	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	408
19.	25.43	Dotriacontane	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	450
20.	26.42	Tetratriacontane	C ₃₄ H ₇₀	478
21.	27.58	Pentatriacontane	C ₃₅ H ₇₂	492
22.	28.96	Tetracontane	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	562
23.	30.57	Hexatriacontane	C ₃₆ H ₇₄	506
24.	32.58	Tetratetracontane	C ₄₄ H ₉₀	618472

Table 6. Fluorescence spectrum of the samples

Sample set	Excitation wavelength (nm)	Emission wavelength range (nm)	Maximum intensity (a.u.)	Wavelength (nm)
Sample I type	343	355–600	623.371	383.84
Sample I type	344	355–600	606.230	386.00
Sample I type	334	350–600	487.207	365.93
Sample I type	340	355–600	396.84	385.07

Table-6 (contd.)

Sample I type	345	355-600	539.065	385.84
Sample I type	345	355-600	490.565	385.84
Sample I type	330	340-600	225.707	365.93
Sample I type	346	355-600	283.366	386.00
Sample II type	334	350-600	118.285	383.07
Sample II type	336	350-600	180.236	386.88
Sample II type	338	350-600	220.254	389.35
Sample II type	335	350-600	140.916	382.42
Market available candle wax sample	315	335-600	645.030	349.06

Table 7. Percentage of wax in the samples

Sl. no	Nature of sample	Weight of sample (g)	Weight of ethereal extract (g)	% of oil/wax
1.	Class I type	2.5290	0.1018	4.02
2.	Class I type	2.6657	0.1348	5.05
3.	Class I type	2.7168	0.0910	3.34
4.	Class I type	2.5662	0.0941	3.6
5.	Class I type	3.6428	0.1786	4.9
6.	Class I type	3.5789	0.1722	4.81
7.	Class I type	2.6737	0.1180	4.41
8.	Class I type	2.6452	0.1639	6.19
9.	Class I type	2.7851	0.1179	4.23
10.	Class I type	2.6900	0.1129	4.19
11.	Class I type	2.6113	0.1051	4.02
12.	Class II type	2.6867	0.2999	11.16
13.	Class II type	2.7632	0.3012	10.90
14.	Class II type	2.6884	0.2410	8.96
15.	Class II type	2.5986	0.2386	9.18
16.	Class II type	2.6282	0.2350	8.94

and fuel oils as verified from the comparison of GC/MS analysis of fuel oil in acetone and with the acetone extracted oil from the explosives. The fuel was invariably fuel 2 but with variations.

However, a large number of explosives presently obtained contained fuels which were partially soluble in acetone but more soluble in ether solutions indicating the possibility of fuels other than fuel oils. The results of the GC/MS of ether solutions invariably contradicts the presence of the fuel oil i.e. the explosives were not really ANFO but fuels were higher boiling hydrocarbons, confirmed from the matching of the GC-MS data of ethereal solutions of explosive residues and ethereal solutions of wax in the candle sticks available in the market.

These are samples received between 2005-2008. It

was also observed that in cases of older exhibits TIC of GC/MS of fuels were quite different from those TIC of GC/MS obtained in ordinary waxes (recent exhibits). The fractions contained dodecano/tetradecano/hexadecano/nonadecano/octadecano/tridecano nitriles and other products. These are available in synthetic/commercial waxes¹⁴. The molecular weight of synthetic waxes was lower compared to those of natural waxes. The melting points of natural waxes were higher and ranged between 50.1-51.1 °C, whereas the melting points of synthetic waxes ranged between 40.1-40.6 °C (Table 8). Paraffin waxes from different sources have similar composition. But there may be differences in their oil content resulting in differences in melting points and sharp melting points are not expected. However, it is clear that the binders of the explosives were waxes but not fuel oil.

The % of oil (wax) in class I type of explosives were low (3.3-6.2%) whereas % of oil (wax) in class II type of explosives were relatively high (8.9-11.2%) probably due to requirement for the preparation of explosive cakes (Table 7).

Table 8. Melting point of the samples

Sl. no.	Nature of sample	Melting point (°C)
1.	Class I type	50.8
2.	Class I type	50.6
3.	Class I type	50.5
4.	Class I type	50.6
5.	Class I type	50.1
6.	Class II type	40.2
7.	Class II type	40.5
8.	Class II type	40.3
9.	Class II type	40.6
10.	Class II type	40.1

The results showed that the explosives were not ANFO in the true sense i.e. no fuel oil was present in the explosive samples.

For replacement of dynamites with comparatively safe and low costly blasting devices for commercial blasting, ANFO (AN + 2 no. fuel oil) was used. For such purposes usually spongy prills of AN having 7-10% porosity to absorb the fuels (no. 2 fuel oil) were used. It was observed that 5-6% fuel is required to soak prilled AN¹⁵. The amount of fuel is just sufficient to have oxygen balance

Mass spectrum of some compounds obtained from sample I (natural wax base) type

Fuel in excess, -ve oxygen balance.

Oxidizer in excess, +ve oxygen balance.

During detonation, fuels get oxidized very fast producing energy, therefore available oxygen for such oxidation reactions is important for the energy production and oxygen balance. ANFO is completely balanced with respect to oxygen yield and maximum energy as shown. However, less costly prills of AN (fertilizer grade AN) having 10 percent bulk density and 3 percent porosity was used¹⁵. AN is not capable to soak or absorb fuels to a large extent. Excess of fuel was to be drained out. The difficulties were avoided by the use of ordinary wax readily available in the market. Moreover prilled AN was not used rather grained AN (less costly) was used to make explosive devices. Liquid wax materials were thoroughly mixed with grained AN with other nitrates, Al etc. to prepare the IED. For proper mixing, grained AN with wax fuel requirement was probably more for synthetic waxes due to low melting point of synthetic wax (Table 8). Solidification of wax could be assumed be faster hindering proper mixing possibilities of solid wax in the explosives. The data suggest that the nature of the fuel with the exhibits were similar, slight changes were due to changes in molecular weight of the hydrocarbon fractions in the waxes. Fuels present in the exhibits showed beautiful fluorescence. It is known that waxes have characteristics fluorescence patterns, depending on the substance, it's physical and chemical origin, manufacture, age, etc.¹⁸. Fluorescence may be due to specific chemical bonding or the radicals which act as light emitters or fluorophors. Fluorescence in impure waxes may be due to phosphor like organic or inorganic impurities dissolved in wax¹⁸. Proper investigation of fluorescence properties of the different wax samples present as fuel in the explosive exhibits may reveal a lot of information related to forensic investigations. Another interesting observation was the presence of 4,6-dinitrocresol (phenol, 2-methyl-4,6-dinitro-/DNOC) ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}$, M.W. 198), a toxic pesticide banned in European Countries since 1999, in some of the exhibits containing synthetic fuel. However, DNOC, may be used as such and could be extracted in ether/acetone

solutions. DNOC, a toxic pesticide with two $-\text{NO}_2$ groups can be utilized as powerful explosive ingredients. Detonation using ANFO mixed with DNOC was carried out in stone quarries for the disposal of DNOC in country like Poland where huge stocks of DNOC were available for disposal even in the recent past¹⁹. It is not clear whether DNOC is used in India as pesticide or it is imported as such in synthetic wax or AN or prepared as such. The observation should be properly examined to find whether DNOC is used in India till now.

Conclusions :

The explosives were found to contain mainly ammonium nitrate (AN) with other minor ingredients together with fuels as binders. No fuel oil was used i.e. the explosives were not ANFO in true senses. The explosives were the handiwork probably of two terrorist groups using ordinary natural waxes and synthetic waxes showing fluorescence. Probably synthetic wax (in older exhibits) was replaced by natural waxes in recent exhibits.

The binders are of great importance in preparing explosive devices. Huge amounts of wax with varied industrial applications are imported in India from abroad in addition to it's own resources. No foreign expertise or groups are probably involved in the preparation of explosives. However, strict vigil is necessary on the use and movement of NH_4NO_3 and waxes.

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